

THE DIFFICULTIES OF READING IN A SECOND LANGUAGE AND THE RESEARCH BASED SOLUTIONS TO MEET THEM

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Annotation: With the increasing importance of globalization and international communication, the ability to read and understand materials in a second language has become a crucial skill for many individuals around the world. However, reading comprehension in a second language is often a challenging task, requiring a complex set of cognitive skills and linguistic knowledge. In this article, I will explore the factors that can make it difficult to comprehend reading materials in a second language, the cognitive processes involved in second language reading comprehension, and the strategies that can be employed to improve reading comprehension in a second language.

Keywords: globalization, cognitive skills, cognitive processes, infer the meaning, background knowledge, decode the written language, syntax, integrate the knowledge, reading fluency.

Factors that make it difficult to comprehend reading materials in a second language

There are a variety of factors that can make it difficult to comprehend reading materials in a second language. One of the most obvious is a lack of vocabulary knowledge. When reading in a second language, readers may encounter unfamiliar words that they are unable to infer the meaning of from context, which can impede their comprehension of the text. Additionally, they may not be familiar with the idiomatic expressions and cultural references that are often used in the language, which can also make it difficult to understand the text.

Another important factor is the reader's background knowledge. When reading in a first language, readers often bring a wealth of background knowledge to the text, including knowledge of the topic, the author, and the cultural context in which the text was written. This background knowledge can help them to make sense of the text and to fill in gaps in their understanding. However, when reading in a second language, readers may not have this same level of background knowledge, which can make it more difficult to comprehend the text.

Cognitive processes involved in second language reading comprehension

Reading comprehension in a second language involves a complex set of cognitive processes. One of the most important is the ability to decode the written language. Readers must be able to recognize and interpret the letters and symbols that make up the words in the text. They must also be able to understand the grammar and syntax of the language in order to make sense of the sentences and paragraphs.

In addition to decoding the written language, readers must also be able to understand the meaning of the words and sentences in the text. This requires a deep knowledge of the vocabulary and grammar of the language, as well as an ability to infer meaning from context and to make connections between different parts of the text.

Finally, readers must be able to integrate their understanding of the text with their background knowledge and prior experiences in order to create a coherent and meaningful

understanding of the text. This requires a high level of cognitive processing and can be particularly challenging when reading in a second language.

Strategies for improving second language reading comprehension

Despite the challenges of reading comprehension in a second language, there are a variety of strategies that can be employed to improve comprehension. One of the most important is to build vocabulary knowledge. This can be done through a variety of methods, including reading extensively in the second language, using flashcards to memorize new vocabulary, and studying vocabulary lists and word roots.

Another important strategy is to develop reading fluency. Reading fluency refers to the ability to read quickly and accurately, without having to stop and decode individual words. Developing reading fluency can help readers to focus on the meaning of the text and to make connections between different parts of the text more easily.

In addition to building vocabulary knowledge and developing reading fluency, readers can also employ a variety of reading strategies to improve comprehension. These strategies include previewing the text before reading, making predictions about the content of the text. Making predictions can be done by looking at the illustrations given along the text. It can also be done by reading the title and trying to understand what is about to come when reading a text.

Yet another way to improve the reading comprehension is through interaction and share of the meaning of text with fellow readers (Casanova 1988). When talking about the text, students obtain literate skills (Heath 1984, Vygotsky 1962) which are crucial in making sense of the reading material. Besides, interaction promotes easier language acquisition and better retention of the information. When working with other learners, students can exchange some of the ways they use to comprehend the texts of a second language. Therefore, learner interaction should be encouraged to assist both language acquisition and improve a reading comprehension.

Furthermore, this particular way may not seem as a solution but a strategy. Second language text readers need to read not the single words, instead they should see the chunks of words to better comprehend the text and avoid distraction (Eskey, 1986; Anderson, 2005). Renowned scholar Krashen (1985) stated that reading skills can be boosted up by reading. It does make sense of course; practice is the key to success. Reading more will equip learners with the self-made strategies and adaptation. Second language texts reading becomes easy by doing it as often as possible. This frequent reading is known as extensive reading (Day and Bamford, 1998).

As stated above, word knowledge plays a crucial role in a second language reading comprehension. However, for many years the right technique has not been found or proven effective which would ease the word memorization process. Although not far in the past (2001-2000), Nation and Coxhead proposed word frequency list which include the most frequently used vocabulary that help students comprehend up to 80% of the reading material.

Conclusion

Ability to read and comprehend in a second language is essential tool to acquire new knowledge. More importantly, second language reading opens the doors for learning other cultures and for enhanced world view. Taking into account the importance of target language reading, we should know the ways in which learners struggle to make a sense of what they

read in a target language and get to know the ways to address those difficulties to assist a learning process. Thus specific thesis discussed the underlying factors and proposed some of the research based solutions to boost up a reading comprehension of second language texts.

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